

DEVELOPING VOCABULARY SKILLS OF NON-SPECIALIST STUDENT WITH HELPING SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING AND IT TOOLS

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Annotation: This article described the pedagogical, psychological and philosophical analysis of the necessary competencies for the functioning of students in the SMM environment, methods for the development of vocabulary skills based on the SMM of students "information technology in education" and the use of the Assessment method in their assessment. In addition, a statistical analysis of the level of development of ICT and SMM competences of non-specialist students of Uzbekiston University of World Languages is given.

Key words: SMM, competence, assessment method, technological map, students of higher education institution.

1 INTRODUCTION

The introduction of information and communication technologies into the world education system requires the development of information and communication competence of teachers. In the European Union, core competencies are defined as a set of skills (basic and new core skills) necessary for living in a modern knowledge society. (2006) The European Parliament and the Council have included the following key competencies for lifelong learning: communication in mother tongue k.; communication in foreign languages, etc.; competence in mathematics, natural sciences and technology; ICT competence ¹. At the same time, the UNESCO program "Development of ICT Competence of Students" is becoming increasingly important in preparing teachers for the effective use of virtual educational technologies.

There is a special need in the world to develop effective models for the development of information and communication competence of future specialists, improve didactic support for the organization and implementation of an innovative and interactive educational environment. Coimbra Group of Universities (University of Coumbre Group) was founded in 1985 and the aim of this institution is to prepare students for their future professions with the help of new innovative technologies and ICT tools. At the same time, they serve to determine the directions of scientific research in the field of developing the information and communication competence of students. ².

At the Uzbek State University of World Languages,

as a priority area for reforming the field of higher education, special attention is paid to the widespread introduction of interactive software tools into the educational process, the rapid development of distance and media education as the "University of the Future". This requires the improvement of pedagogical mechanisms for the development of information and communication competence of teachers. In the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, an important task is "improving the quality and efficiency of the activities of higher educational institutions based on the introduction of international standards for assessing the quality of education and teaching." These tasks show that the improvement of the content and the practical and technological system for the development of information and communication competence of teachers in the process of advanced training based on modern approaches is relevant.

2 METHODOLOGY

Information development is accelerating not only in social networks, but also in all types of education. At this stage of human development, social networks occupy one of the most important places in the digital technology market. The number of social media users worldwide has reached 10 billion. In the last 12 months alone, this figure has increased to 1,490 million, an increase of more than 30 percent over the same period last year. In 2022, 90.6% of the world's population will use social media. Such dynamics gives reason to believe that social networks are

¹ <http://www.ibe.unesco.org/en/glossary-curriculum-terminology/k/key-competencescompetencies-or-skills>

² <http://www.coimbra-group.eu/>

the future, therefore they are the most important means of influence today.

The purpose of this article is to develop the vocabulary of students studying in a non-special direction in the Republic of Uzbekistan on the basis of ICT and SMM.

In the process of studying this problem, studies of foreign, CIS and Uzbek scientists on the use of SMM in education and technical encyclopedias on concepts were analyzed, as well as problems aimed at developing the vocabulary of non-specialist students based on ICT and SMM and ways to solve them were comprehensively analyzed.

According to many explanatory dictionaries and Internet sources, SMM is social media marketing, that is, social media marketing, where its main goal is to earn money or distribute advertising through Internet networks. But the question arises whether the introduction of such an Internet tool in education will increase the effectiveness of education. In our opinion, the introduction of SMM into the educational process will serve to improve the quality of the educational process, as well as the introduction of the concepts of podcast and vodcast and precast in accordance with the requirements of the time.³[1]

The use of social media marketing in education and the use of its tools is often found in the online form of education or in the form of online courses and workshops for students with disabilities, students who, for whatever reason, cannot participate in classes. [2]

However, in recent years, many theorists and practitioners of the scientific community have presented many arguments in favor of distance education. The rapid development of the world, the general digitalization of information and the development of information and communication technologies have made many changes in the education system. Many new terms have appeared, such as "webinar", "online conference", "online school", "online course" and other terminology of related characteristics. However, despite the development of technology and the change in the way of studying the course, the problem of communication between students is sharply exacerbated. [3]

In the works of many scientists, analysts and Internet bloggers on the problems of distance development, different opinions were expressed about the appropriateness and effectiveness of this form of education. [4]

E. A. Neretina, A. B. Makares in the article "Possibilities and limitations of using marketing in social networks to promote the educational services of the

university" believe that marketing in social networks is a new direction of establishing contact with consumers of educational services. They claim that this opens up completely new opportunities for them to communicate with consumers and provide instant feedback.⁴[5]

We must correct the necessity of individual information competence of the students who are using UN in order to conduct research. In the table below, we present the rates of scientists for the concepts of social media marketing competence and competence in education.[6]

Table 1: Opinions of scientists on the necessary competencies and competencies of students in the SMM environment

Authors	The concept of "competence"	"Explanation of the concept of "competence".
Ojegov S.I. ⁵	A range of issues that are very well mastered by the individual	Some kind of industry awareness, leadership
Zimny I.A. ⁶	A system of individual internal potential, latent psychological renewal (knowledge, imagination, program of action, values and attitudes).	Hidden, potential knowledge that is not used in practice, knowledge, skills, qualifications arising from the intellectual and conditioned experiences of a person's socio-professional activity
Khutorskoy A.V. ⁷	A set of interrelated qualities of a person reflected in the requirements for graduate educational preparation	Acquisition of relevant competencies by the individual
Vyalikova G.S. ⁸	1) in-depth knowledge acquired with information on a specific subject; 2) some authority, scope of rights	Specific training is a description of a person performing a task within a range of abilities and specific competencies

³

<https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/03074800610713299/full/html>

⁴ <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/vozmozhnosti-i-ogranicheniya-ispolzovaniya-marketinga-v-sotsialnyh-media-dlya-prodvizheniya-obrazovatelnyh-uslug-vuza>

⁵ Dictionary of the Russian language: 70,000 words / Ed. N.Yu. Shvedova. - 23rd ed., Rev. - M.: Rus. yaz., 1991. - S. 288

⁶ Key competencies - a new paradigm of the result of education // J. Higher education today. - M.: 2003. - No. 5. - P. 45.

⁷ Key competencies and educational standards // www.eidos.ru/news/compet.htm

⁸ Pedagogical stimulation of the teacher's professional competence in the conditions of distance learning: Abstract of the thesis. dis. ... doc. ped. Sciences. - Ryazan, 2006. - P. 29.

Pankova T. V.⁹	Knowledge of a specific field of science, a set of knowledge, skills, and competencies formed in the educational process, expressing thinking using its categories	Specific training that determines the subject's ability to perform some activity based on existing competencies (or a set of competencies)
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V.F. Burmakina expresses it in the form of "Digital technologies, means of communication, transmission of information over networks providing access to information, management, integration of digital technologies, means of communication, networks providing access to information, assessment of their use in modern society", Novikova Z.N." The user acknowledges that his activity consists in the use of computers and information technology as a means of information technology and the use of SMM¹⁰ [7].

In our opinion, the opinion expressed by V. F. Burmakina is not aimed at clarifying the essence of the concept of "information and communication literacy", but at assessing the current situation in terms of digital technologies, means of communication, networks that provide the possibility of obtaining and exchanging information in the SMM, and their use and transmission of information. His approach to this process determines his attitude.

The definition of Z. N. Novikova needs substantial improvement. Because the use of computer and information technologies by a teacher in their professional activities is considered a high level of modern SMM literacy.[8]

According to a study conducted by M. Hepworth, information literacy is the ability to recognize the need to obtain the necessary information, determine its basis with the help of ICT, find it, evaluate it and use it effectively in solving a specific problem.¹¹ [9].

The concepts of "SMM" and "computer competence" are also used in linguistic usage. At the same time, it should be noted that such concepts as "modern concepts and terms of HMM", "computer competence" with the characteristics of information and communication competence of a person to create modern applications, programs and teaching aids in the requirements of HMM, to use them in the training process, for illumination of labor abilities serves. [10]

3 DISCUSSION

At the State University of World Languages of Uzbekistan, in the curriculum of the subject "Information Technologies in Education", 120 credits were allocated at the Department of "Modern Information

Technologies". Among the topics covered in this topic, the following can be considered.

Students in Science:

- Independently thinking, intellectually developed, having their own worldview, can use the acquired theoretical knowledge, practical skills and competencies in solving practical and theoretical problems in their daily lives and apply them in practice.

- they can also rationally use the requirements (norms) of marketing in social networks, imposed on a predetermined educational background of a student, necessary for effective creative activity in a certain field.

- to learn the formalized art of applying knowledge, skills and experience in professional activities.

Form of training: practical training (A)		
Code	Subject Name	Ball
A 1	Information and its application in various fields.	3
A 2	Android mobile operating system.	3
A 3	Viruses and antivirus programs.	3
A 4	Creating a Modern Intellectual Dictionary	3
A 5	Multimedia and its modern support.	3
A 6	Use of multimedia in information provision.	3
A 7	Using the Internet in Distance Education.	3
A 8	GOOGLE CHROME program capabilities.	3
A 9	Interactive services of professional information systems	3
A10	Information request systems. Information communication systems.	3
A11	Automated job numbering and features.	3
A12	Information security and information protection methods.	3
A13	Information systems and their types.	3
A14	Electronic digital signature software.	3
A 15	Virtual laboratories.	3
Total:		30

One of the themes has been used for a clearer and more up-to-date development through the Evaluation Method below.

Assessment method. The assessment method is widely used in modern education. It is concluded that the use of this technique will help to achieve the expected result when organizing research on the development of information and communication competence and IMM (marketing in social networks) among the audience. Therefore, the assessment method is useful in determining whether a person has theoretical and

⁹ Essence, content and structure of information and communication competence of a university student // Nauch.-met. Electron. and "Concept". - M.: 2013. - T. 4. - S. 206-210.

¹⁰ <https://ifap.ru/library/book360.pdf>

¹¹ <https://www.semanticscholar.org/author/M.-Hepworth/144706318>

practical knowledge, a creative approach to the problem under study in terms of its essence and didactic potential.

The method usually includes at least four types of tasks. By the nature of the tasks, the ability to interpret the basic concepts of the topic (question-answer, blitz survey, interview), possession of theoretical knowledge (test), ability to apply them in practice, mastery of skills (practical task, case), reaction to situations that reflect the problem May be in the form of (creative project). During the research, attention is paid to the use of open and closed tests, creative projects in the form of presentations, video riddles, various puzzles (crosswords, scanwords, anagrams, puzzles, etc.). When organizing the study, evaluation tasks were formed according to the following schemes:

1) blitz survey - open test - case - creative project (puzzle);

2) question-answer - closed test - case - creative project (presentation);

3) interview - open test - case - creative project (video riddle).

We believe that these topics will help students apply their knowledge in practical life, use modern technologies, methods, mobile applications, SMM and make the level of knowledge very modern in the future.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This section includes a technological map on the topic "Creation of modern intellectual vocabulary".

Time: 2 hours	Number of students: 12-15 people
Type of lesson:	Practical training
Practical training plan:	1. A list of several programs and platforms is formed, including Crunch VS Hashcat, iSping... 2. Learning interface of the program. 3. Topics are presented in different directions.
The purpose of the training: to strengthen the knowledge gained by students in lectures and practical training, to develop practical skills and competencies.	
Pedagogical tasks	Learning Outcomes
1. Explain the purpose of practical work on the topic and the procedure for completing the modern task. 2. Assisting in the performance of tasks, developing skills and competencies, providing video lessons. 3. Independent assignments	A student 1. understanding the purpose and tasks of practical work on the topic. 2. Completion of assignments, formation of practical skills and competencies. 3. Gives independent assignments
Teaching methods and techniques	The intellectual vocabulary program is calculated and used in education.
Teaching aids	educational-methodological complex: handouts, tests.

	Visual aids: slides, electronic textbooks, audio sounds.
Form of the lesson	Personal, small group work, online group technology.
Training conditions	Projector, computer-equipped auditorium, mobile devices connected to the Internet.
Monitoring and evaluation	Practical work, Assessment survey, presentation of the program, application on mobile devices or on a computer. analysis of results (evaluation)

In the course of the study, in the process of developing the information and communication competence of students and SMM, assessment tasks were formed in several versions for the respondents-listeners.

In the course of the study, with the development of the information and communication competence of students and SMM, non-standard tests were offered to the attention of the respondents-listeners to examine the modern educational competence of SMM. In total, 273 people were involved in the test work, an average of 58 respondents from each experimental area. The share of the total number of respondents by fields of activity was as follows.

Table 2: Number of respondents by field of experience

№	Fields of experience	Number of respondents	In interest
1.	Faculty of international journalism	92	33,8
2.	Faculty of translation	87	31,8
3.	Faculty of romano-germanic philology	94	34,4
	Total	273	100

Table 3: Response indicators of student respondents (substantiating and emphasizing experience)

Groups	Number of listeners	Degree indicators					
		High		Medium		Lower	
		Experience first	End of experiment	Experience a first	End of experiment	Experience first	End of experiment
Experience	134	32	50	40	59	62	25
Control	139	31	35	43	46	65	58

Table 4: Percentage expression of indicators of performance of practical tasks by respondents-listeners (emphasizing experience)

Groups	Number of students	Quantitative and percentage expression of degree indicators					
		High		Medium		Lower	
		Quantitative indicator	Percentage indicator	Quantitative indicator	Percentage indicator	Quantitative indicator	Percentage indicator
Experience	134	50	37,3	59	44	25	18,7
Control	139	35	25,2	46	33,1	58	41,7

In order to more clearly express the difference between the results of both groups, the totals of the experiment can be expressed as a percentage.

For statistical analysis, the performance indicators of practical tasks recorded at the end of the experiment in both groups were taken. For statistical analysis, the criterion (method) of Student-Fisher was chosen, which has been widely used in recent years in pedagogical research. This method allows, from a statistical point of view, to express the difference between the practical professional skills and qualifications of the respondents-listeners of the experimental and control groups.

According to the content of the methodology, the indicators recorded at the end of the experiment in the experimental and control groups were taken as a sample. At the same time, the indicators of the experimental group were called table 1, and the indicators of the control group were called table 2.

The values for these samples were determined by the indicators, as indicated:

Table 4: According to the indicators of selections 1 and 2, the following diagram is created:

Selections	Groups	Mathematical expression	Degree indicators		
			High	Medium	Low
Selection 1	Experiment $m, n \square 134$	X_i	50	59	25
Selection 2	Control $n, n \square 139$	Y_i	35	46	58

In conclusion, the following conclusions were presented based on the results of a study conducted on the topic "Creation of a modern intellectual dictionary":

- As a result of the introduction of the achievements of science and technology in pedagogical activity, it serves the development of information and communication competence and IMM in the person of the teacher, and the effective provision of the educational process.
- Based on the development of information and communication competence, mastering the need of students to master the functionality of SMM technologies (motivational level), full familiarization with them (cognitive level), consistent and effective use of information and communication technologies for the implementation of pedagogical goals, the creation of a creative product (active-reflexive level).

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